

EVENT TOURISM AS A SIGNIFICANT PART OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONS IN KAZAKHSTAN

Demeubayeva R.

EMBA, DBA Doctoral Student

Almaty Management University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16995185>

Abstract

Event tourism is currently becoming a rapidly growing area of domestic tourism in Kazakhstan. Event tourism is one of the most important factors in regional development, contributing to increased recognition and a rise in the number of repeat tourist visits. Researchers most often view event tourism as a type of tourist activity that attracts tourists with diverse public events in cultural or sports life, which contribute to the development of tourism infrastructure, the integration of different segments of society, and the formation of a positive image of the region.

Keywords: Tourism, event tourism, event tourism management, local development, economic development, development of region.

Most developing countries actively compete with each other in the battle for tourists, improving the quality of existing events and coming up with new ones, thereby developing a relatively young and promising area of the tourism business – event tourism. Event tourism began its development abroad, but in recent years it has firmly entered the lexicon of tourism professionals in Kazakhstan, adding to the list of types of domestic and inbound tourism.

In the current economic downturn, event tourism should contribute to the growth of domestic regional products, the diversification of regional budget revenue sources, job creation, and the improvement of the population's quality of life. Since the creation and promotion of new, globally recognized events requires significant financial investment, large-scale marketing research, thoughtful management, long-term engagement of potential visitors through PR campaigns, and a sufficient number of professionals—in other words, many things that Kazakhstan lacks—it makes no sense, in the author's opinion, to talk about a significant increase in the role of event tourism in the near future and within the entire country. Based on previous studies, there is an opinion that events will be much more effective at the regional level. Holding events is much more profitable for small regional and municipal budgets. Revenues from event tourism at the regional level can be much higher than for the country as a whole. It also should be taken into account the factor of destinations that are attractive to tourists, combining factors: climate, geographical location, quality of tourist infrastructure, historical and cultural potential, etc [1].

Practically all regions of our country host a variety of themed festivals, business events, cultural, entertainment, and sporting events, which contributes to an increase in tourist flow. It is event tourism that has become a driver of development for many cities and individual settlements in the country, contributing to the creation of special regional tourism products. The variety of events and their thematic focus make it possible to realize the potential of virtually any territory.

Event tourism is a unique format because it is very multifaceted in terms of content. Event tourism is based on events of various kinds: cultural, historical, sporting, ethnographic, gastronomic, etc. The holding of various

large-scale events plays an important role in the revival of territories and cities, contributes to the representation of territorial and urban space, and makes a significant contribution to increasing the tourist and investment attractiveness of a destination [2].

In today's world, there is clearly growing competition between regions not only for tourists but also for investors. Event tourism provides an opportunity to introduce potential consumers to new features and resources of a region, increase its visibility and tourist appeal, and actively promote the region at the national level. In addition, such events trigger a multiplier effect and are very effective for the region's economy, as they involve the use of services and goods from local suppliers and producers.

Traditionally, event tourism is seen as a type of tourism where trips are planned around specific events or activities.

Let us highlight the important features of event tourism:

- a direct link between the purpose of the trip and the event taking place in a specific location and during a specific period of time. The temporal and periodic nature of the event is significantly more important than the seasonality of this type of tourism;
- the event that is the purpose of the tour must be original and authentic. Only in this case does the tourist have sufficient reason to spend time and money traveling to the area where the event is planned;
- the desire, interest, and willingness of local residents to support and participate in the event;
- the opportunity to participate directly in the event or to empathize with it [3].

The event itself is the main focus when organizing a tour. However, event-based tourism, like tourism in general, rarely does without traditional visits to cultural and historical attractions or other tourist sites. The opportunity to taste local cuisine or buy local souvenirs. All of this, in synergy, significantly improves tourists' impressions of the area and makes event-based tour products more in demand and popular. Many leading experts predict, and not without reason, that in the near

future the number of visitors to various events will exceed the number of participants in traditional cultural and educational tours.

When organizing event tourism as a type of tourist activity, it is necessary to pay special attention to the main components of the tourism and hospitality industry: accommodation, catering, transportation, information, management, and staffing [2].

The prospects for this type of tourism are explained by some of its unique features. When we talk about event tourism, we are not talking about events in their pure form—we are talking about adapting good events to accommodate organized and unorganized tourist flows. The second feature is the absence of seasonality, which means that event tourism can be developed year-round.

According to foreign authors in the field the impact of events on the tourism potential of a region, we need to look at two different time frames. In the short term, it's about increasing tourist traffic, including during the low season. Thanks to the brand component, it's easier for tour operators and other companies in the tourism industry to promote their products [4]. For example, if an event takes place once a year, it is limited to that period in terms of attracting tourist traffic. But if a tourist brand operates in the region, then the event works for that region all year round. A well-organized event is considered an effective tool for regional marketing — a tool for attracting attention to the region and promoting its interests.

In summary, it can be noted that event tourism can play an important role in solving the socio-economic problems of Kazakhstan. At the same time, it is particularly important to include event tourism in the long-term development programs of regions and cities, which should contain mechanisms for subsidizing funds for the creation and operation of tourist infrastructure, developing plans for training personnel for the tourism and hospitality sector, implementing a set of measures in the field of information support for events, etc.

In today's world, the tourism services market has become one of the most important segments of the services market, both in individual countries and in the

global economy as a whole. At the same time, under the influence of current economic and social processes, changes are taking place in the very structure of the tourism services market, with new segments emerging and the role and significance of others diminishing. In particular, a segment of this market known as event tourism has emerged and is strengthening its position. It can be concluded that event tourism is multifaceted, an attractive tool for promoting territories and regions, and a relatively new direction in tourism in Kazakhstan.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the development of the territory cannot be imagined without the development of tourism as a whole, and event tourism is a new but promising direction. The opportunities offered by event tourism should not be ignored when developing domestic tourism in the country, as it is based on a specific event, and human imagination is limitless, allowing for the creation of ever new and interesting events. Event tourism does not require the presence of unique tourist resources, and in this regard, we note its significance for regions and territories that are not highly attractive but are striving to improve their rating even during economic crises.

References:

1. Laing, J., & Frost, W. (2015). Setting a research agenda for rituals and traditional events. In J. Laing, & W. Frost (Eds.). *Rituals and Traditional Events in the Modern World* (pp. 232–245). Abingdon, OX and New York: Routledge.
2. Panfiluk, E. (2015b). Impact of a tourist event of a regional range on the development of Tourism. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 213, 1020–1027. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.11.520>
3. Ovcharov, A. O. (2015). Methodological Problems of Statistical Study of regional tourism and tourist expenditure. *Economy of Region*, 281–287. <https://doi.org/10.17059/2015-1-25>
4. Sak, M., Eren, S., & Bayram, G. E. (2022a). Role of event tourism in Economic Development. *Event Tourism in Asian Countries*, 249–265. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003161134-14>